

**“ CORRELATION OF ULTRASOUND WITH MRI SHOULDER JOINT OF
ROTATOR CUFF TEAR IN POPULATION OF VIJAYAPURA ”**

BY

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Under the guidance of

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

US	-	Ultrasound
MRI	-	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
MRA-		Magnetic Resonance Arthrography
SPSS	-	Statistical package for the social sciences
SD	-	Standard Deviation
NPV	-	Negative Predictive Value
PPV	-	Positive Predictive Value
CI	-	Confidence interval
SCJ	-	Sternoclavicular Joint
GHJ	-	Glenohumeral Joint.
UL	-	Upper Limb
BMI-		Body mass index
HDL-		High density lipoprotein
RC-		Rotator Cuff

ABSTRACT

Aims:

- The study aims to detect the efficiency of ultrasound because it is a readily available, inexpensive, and dynamic study compared to MRI for detecting rotator cuff tears.

Methods:

- The study protocol was approved by the institutional review board.
- The sample size in our study is 53.
- Patients with complaints of shoulder pain and dysfunction were subjected to Ultrasound and MRI shoulder.
- The diagnostic tests of sensitivity, specificity, positive and negative predictive values and accuracy were computed after comparing the ultrasound results with the MRI shoulder scan.

Results: A hospital based prospective study was conducted to compare ultrasound with MRI shoulder in rotator cuff tears. The study showed a significant agreement with ultrasound and MRI shoulder in detection of rotator cuff tear with P-Value of <0.05 . The sensitivity and specificity of detecting of rotator cuff tears was 91.2% and 81.8% with overall accuracy of 88.6%.

Keywords: Ultrasound, MRI, rotator cuff tears, partial-thickness and full-thickness tears.

INTRODUCTION

Human shoulder joint can move which represents a complex, well-balanced anatomic system that can apply force in a variety of directions and orientations.

The gleno-humeral joint primarily facilitates movement in the shoulder, while the scapulothoracic articulation also contributes significantly. The upper limb and scapula are connected through the acromio-clavicular joint and sternoclavicular joint (SCJ). The shallow cup formed by the glenoid and the relatively large humeral head enables a wide range of motion at the shoulder. However, this design is inherently unstable, likened to balancing a golf ball on a tee. Numerous dynamic and static structures support the stability of the glenohumeral joint (GHJ). The dynamic structures include the rotator cuff muscle, scapular and deltoid muscles(1). The static structures include the glenoid labrum and associated capsuloligamentous components(1).

The four muscles that form the "rotator cuff" are those that support the humeral head. Their tendons are inserted at the smaller and greater tuberosities, and they arise from the front and back aspects of the scapula. Rotator cuff muscles consist of the subscapularis (supports shoulder anteriorly), the supraspinatus(supports shoulder superiorly, the infraspinatus and teres minor(supports from posterior aspect) (2).

“Shoulder pain and limitation of motion are widespread causes of quality of life impairment, medical resource use and loss of workplace productivity”(3). The most common reason for shoulder pain and dysfunction is rotator cuff pathology like calcific tendinosis, degeneration tears and bursitis(4).

“Rotator cuff failure occurs as a result of tendinopathy changes that change from partial to full-thickness tears involving mainly the supraspinatus tendon and may proceed to involve the infraspinatus tendon and/or the subscapularis tendon”(5). The rotator cuff failure occurs most commonly after the age of 40 years, and in young people, the rotator cuff failure is uncommon and mainly occurs in athletes due to acute injuries(6).

A rotator cuff tear occurs when the muscle fibres of supraspinatus, infraspinatus, teres minor and subscapularis are disrupted or detached. Among these muscles, the supraspinatus is commonly affected. Rotator cuff tears can be classified into two types: full-thickness (involving complete disruption) and partial-thickness tears(7). Tears can occur due to external impingement, trauma, degenerative changes, lifting heavy weights and joint instability(2).

Risk elements for tears in rotator cuff:

The risk factors for rotator cuff tears are multiple and is categorized into internal and external risk factors.

The external factors are:

- Os Acromiale
- Morphology of coracoid process and acromion.
- Spurs from acromial process.

The intrinsic factors are:

- Tendon degeneration.
- Vascular micro-supply.
- Genetic factors.

Other risk factors:

- Male gender.
- Increased age.
- Trauma.
- Dominant hand.
- Higher body mass index (BMI).
- Lower high-density lipoprotein (HDL).
- Smoking.
- Lifting heavy weights, repetitive work and awkward posture.

Patients who have tears in their rotator cuffs often complain of shoulder pain and limited mobility. “Rotator cuff tears are the most common root cause of shoulder pain, occurring in approximately 65% - 70% of patients”(8). Many imaging procedures have been used to assess shoulder pain; however, unenhanced MRI, indirect, direct MR arthrography, and ultrasound are the primary imaging modalities for identifying rotator cuff injuries(9).

In hospital settings, shoulder ultrasound is being used more often to evaluate the rotator cuff's integrity. It is a non-invasive test that has no negative consequences with advantage of performing dynamic examination of the tendons during movement of shoulder(10). The ultrasound shoulder has a disadvantage of being operator dependent with a long learning curve (11), especially in cases of partial thickness tears for which a high interobserver variability is present(12). It has limitation in examination of labrum, rotator cuff interval and detecting subtle bony lesions. “The sensitivity is affected in obese patients and patients with severe shoulder movement restriction”(13).

Plain magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is a static modality but it is preferable because it can provide high-resolution imaging in several planes. An intra-articular injection of a radiopaque dye (called magnetic resonance arthrography(MRA)) can improve its diagnostic potential by highlighting shoulder anomalies and helping to distinguish between intra-articular structures.

Introduction

While MRA is superior to conventional MRI in evaluating shoulder diseases, particularly rotator cuff integrity, the drawbacks of this invasive procedure must be weighed against the potential benefits. Additionally, MRA requires a radiology specialist with advanced training.

“The disadvantages of MRI include availability, time consuming, expensive in addition to its absolute contraindications for patients with intracerebral aneurysm clips, biostimulators, cardiac pacemakers, automatic defibrillators, metallic orbital foreign bodies, cochlear implants and implanted infusion devices”(2).

In this research, I will evaluate the relationship between ultrasound and MRI, using MRI shoulder as the gold standard. By comparing the effectiveness of ultrasound with MRI shoulder in the diagnosis of rotator cuff tears, we can lower the cost of these tests, employ ultrasound in situations when MRI shoulder is not available, and diagnose rotator cuff tears in patients who are contraindicated for MRI.

OBJECTIVES

The purpose of this study is to assess the diagnostic effectiveness of ultrasonography, which is a cost effective, accessible, and dynamic method for diagnosing rotator cuff tears, in comparison to MRI.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview of rotator cuff injuries:

The most prevalent cause of shoulder discomfort (14)(15), shoulder joint restriction is rotator cuff injuries and third most common cause of musculoskeletal pain (behind back and knee pain) (16).

Rotator cuff tears are known to increase with age; more than 50% of adults over 80years have rotator cuff tears. In a study conducted by Yamamoto A, et al. in Japan, rotator cuff tears were assessed in 683 individuals (1,366 shoulders) from a mountain hamlet with an average age of 57.9years and showed prevalence of 20.7%. 36% of patients with symptoms had a rotator cuff injury, compared to 16.9% of those who did not have symptoms(17).

In a meta-analysis, Reilly P. et al. shown the prevalence of rotator cuff tears in cadaveric studies (of 2553 shoulders investigated, 11.75% had complete thickness tears and 18.49% had partial thickness tears; a total of 30.24% of the shoulders had tears, with a mean age of 70.1 years). To look for rotator cuff tears in both symptomatic and asymptomatic patients, tests using magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and ultrasound (USG) were carried out. USG revealed a 41.4% prevalence among symptomatic patients in a sample of 1038

participants (the prevalence for partial thickness tears was 6.7% and the full thickness tear prevalence was 34.7% of mean age 50.4 years). Among 490 patients in the sample, the MRI prevalence was 49.38% (partial thickness tears: 8.57%, full thickness tears: 40.81%; mean age: 43.6 years). Using a sample size of 591, the US found that among the asymptomatic patients, the prevalence of rotator cuff injuries was 38.9% (partial thickness tear: 17.2%, full thickness tear: 21.7%). As opposed to this, a 271-person MRI sample size showed a prevalence of 26.2% (with a mean age of 44.3 years and partial and full thickness tears of 15.87% and 10.33%, respectively) (18).

A study conducted by Abate M, et al in Italy in asymptomatic women showed “the prevalence of rotator cuff tears was more in postmenopausal women (8.9%) when compared to premenopausal women” (19).

The first descriptions of the ultrasound evaluation for rotator cuff tears were published in 1984 by Crass et al. and Middleton et al. (20)(21), which demonstrated that ultrasound is just as accurate as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) in detecting supraspinatus tendon tears.

In 2004 Teefey et al. did a study that showed an overall 87% accuracy rate for both modalities in correctly diagnosing rotator cuff injuries, partial and full thickness. 45 of the 46 full thickness tears and 13 of the 19 partial thickness tears in the study were correctly identified by ultrasound, while 12 of the 19 partial thickness tears and all 46 full thickness tears were accurately identified by magnetic resonance imaging. More than 90% of ultrasound reports showed that the technology can identify tears of any size, whether they are partial or full thickness(22).

In a 2015 study, Samira Sarya and Rehab El Bakry compared shoulder MRI and ultrasound imaging, found that tendinitis could be detected with 90% accuracy, 86% negative predictive value, and 85% sensitivity. The findings for sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV), and accuracy for partial thickness tears were 88%, 89%, 94%, 80%, and 83%, respectively. However, in full thickness tears, 90% accuracy is achieved with 100% sensitivity and specificity(23).

In a 2016 study, Narvir Singh Chauhan and colleagues in North India found that for the diagnosis of rotator cuff tears, there was statistically excellent agreement between ultrasound and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI); ultrasound showed

86.7% sensitivity and 100% specificity for full-thickness tears and 89.7% sensitivity and 98.8% specificity for partial-thickness tears; observed accuracy was 95.9% for partial-thickness tears and 98.4% for full-thickness tears. The Kappa coefficient of association for full thickness tears was 0.91, and for partial thickness tears, it was 0.90(24).

Rotator cuff tear-related impairment:

Tears in the rotator cuff limit everyday mobility. In a study conducted by Japanese academics Nakajima et al. Approximately 99 shoulders (average age 70.5 years) out of 924 experienced tears, while 825 shoulders (average age 60.2 years) did not. The simple shoulder test was used to evaluate daily living activities (SST). Patients with rotator cuff injuries had significantly lower SST scores ($P < 0.001$) when compared to those without the tear. Those with rotator cuff injuries showed a significant association between their ability to sleep through the night and their incapacity to elevate 3.6 kg of weight above shoulder level (25).

ANATOMY OF SHOULDER JOINT

AND ROTATOR CUFF

The glenohumeral joint, which allows for the most movement in the human body, is primarily facilitated by the scapulo-thoracic articulation. The acromio-clavicular and sterno-clavicular joints allow the upper limb and scapular to articulate with the trunk.

Glenohumeral Joint:

The glenoid fossa of the scapula is smaller than humeral head, resulting in a relatively shallow glenoid-humeral joint. At the sacrifice of stability, this arrangement offers a large range of movement. The arrangement is fundamentally unstable and has been compared to a golf ball on a tee.

Type of joint:

Ball and socket type of synovial joint.

Articular Surfaces:

The glenoid cavity and humeral head constitute for the articular surfaces. For this reason, it is sometimes referred to as the glenohumeral articulation.

Due to the glenoid fossa's inability to securely hold the humerus head in place, the joint is weak structurally. Nonetheless, there is a lot of mobility with this configuration.

- The following factors preserve the joint's stability:
 - The coraco-acromial arch, or secondary socket which houses the humerus head.
 - Shoulder's muscular-tendinous cuff.
 - The glenoid fossa is deepened with assistance of the glenoid labrum.
 - The muscles that join the humerus to the pectoral girdle as well as other muscles like the long heads of the triceps and biceps brachii contribute to stability.
 - The joint is also stabilised by atmospheric pressure.

Ligaments of Joint:

- **Capsular ligament:** A highly loose ligament that envelops the joint and facilitates its freedom of motion. In the inferior region of the joint, where dislocations are most common, the ligament provides the least support.

Attachments:

- **Medially:** attached to the scapula past the labrum's borders and the supraglenoid tubercle.
- **Laterally:** The ligament connects to the anatomical neck of the humerus, but there are specific variations: at the lower part, the connection of the ligament reaches to the surgical neck, and at the upper part, there is a gap that allows for the tendon of the biceps brachii's long head to pass through.
- **Anteriorly:** Capsule is strengthened by the supplemental bands called the superior, middle and inferior gleno-humeral ligaments.
 - **Superior gleno-humeral ligament:** Originates from the superior glenoid and extends to the humeral fovea capitis, about one centimetre in front of the bicep's origin. Often identified on cross-sectional imaging.
 - **Middle glenohumeral ligament:** Most erratic in terms of thickness and course often develops in common with the superior glenohumeral ligament and extends antero-infero-laterally to the humerus's smaller tuberosity.
 - **Inferior glenohumeral ligament:** It is a complex ligament with discrete anterior and posterior bands that are divided by

the axillary pouch. Extends from a broad base to the humeral neck, running along the middle and inferior labrum. The most crucial stabiliser, protecting against dislocation from anteriorly and posteriorly.

- **Coracohumeral ligament:** This structure spans from the coracoid process root to the humerus neck. It provides support for the humerus when the arms are at rest by one's side, stabilizes the biceps tendon within its groove, and reinforces the capsule.
- **Transverse humeral ligament:** The transverse humeral ligament connects the lesser and greater tubercles of the humerus and runs across the bicipital groove. It serves to secure the long head of the biceps brachii tendon in place.
- **Glenoid labrum:** A meniscus-like fibrous or fibrocartilaginous structure deepens the glenoid, providing increased contact area and stability for the glenohumeral joint. Between the labrum and the origin of the long head of the biceps brachii muscle, a synovium-lined recess may be present. Anteriorly, extending to the mid-glenoid, the labrum may be absent or unattached, creating a smooth foramen between itself and the glenoid rim. Additionally, a sublabral recess or foramen might exist in this region.

- **Coracoacromial ligament:** It lies beneath the deltoid muscle and above the subacromial-subdeltoid bursa, providing support against upward pressure in the shoulder
- **Coracoclavicular ligament:**
 - Consists of:
 - **Trapezoid ligament:** Trapezoid ligament goes from coracoid process to undersurface of distal clavicle.
 - **Coronoid ligament:** Runs from coracoid to the more medially located conoid tubercle of the clavicle.
- **Acromioclavicular ligament:** Helps in tightening the acromi-clavicular joint capsule and stabilizing the acromio-clavicular joint.

A

B

Figure 1. A) Synovial membrane and joint capsule of gleno-humeral joint. B) Capsule of right gleno-humeral joint (26).

MUSCLES OF SHOULDER JOINT

ROTATOR CUFF MUSCLES:

The four muscles of rotator cuffs which are dynamic stabilisers comprising of subscapularis, teres minor, infraspinatus, and supraspinatus which plays a crucial role in the movement of shoulder joint. Notably, the subscapularis inserts into the lesser tuberosity of the humerus, while the other muscles originate from the scapula and insert into the greater tuberosity

Supraspinatus muscle:

The supraspinatus muscle originates from the medial two-thirds of the supraspinous fossa of the scapula. It inserts into the upper impression of the greater tuberosity of the humerus and contributes some fibres to the superior aspect of the fibrous capsule. Innervated by the suprascapular nerve (C5, C6), it assists in initiating and maintaining arm abduction, working alongside other scapular muscles to stabilize the humeral head during arm movement. Additionally, the supraspinatus plays a role in the initial phase of abduction, which can lead to tendon degeneration, frequent tendinosis and tears.

Infraspinatus muscle: The infraspinatus muscle originates from the medial two-thirds of the scapula's infraspinous fossa. It inserts into the middle impression on the larger tubercle of the humerus. Innervated by the suprascapular nerve (C5, C6), this muscle facilitates lateral rotation of the arm.

Subscapularis: Multipennate, triangular-shaped muscle that attaches to the lesser tubercle of the humerus after emerging from the medial two thirds of the subscapular fossa. Few muscle fibres are supplied to the joint capsule's anterior surface. Both the lower and upper subscapular nerves supply it. Arm adduction and medial rotation are the functions of the muscle.

Teres Minor: The supraspinatus muscle originates from the upper two-thirds of the lateral border's dorsal surface of the scapula. It inserts into the upper impression of the greater tubercle of the humerus and contributes some fibres to the inferior aspect of the joint capsule. Innervated by the axillary nerve (C5, C6), it assists in lateral rotation of the arm and plays a role in stabilizing the humeral head during arm movement. Additionally, the supraspinatus is involved in initiating abduction, which can lead to tendon degeneration and frequent tendinosis and tears.

Figure 2. A) Illustration of rotator cuff muscles from its origin to insertion from anterior aspect. B) Posterior aspect(27).

Deltoid Muscle:

Large and multipennate, the deltoid muscle originates from the anterior border and adjacent surface of the lateral 1/3rd of the clavicle, lower lip of the crest of the scapula spine, lateral border of the acromion. Muscle attaches itself to the humerus's deltoid tuberosity. It is supplied by the axillary nerve which helps in arm abduction at the shoulder joint upto 90-degree angle.

Bursas of the joint:

- Sub-acromial and sub-deltoid bursa which are commonly continuous with each other but sometimes may be separated.
- Sub-scapularis bursa communicating with joint cavity.
- Infraspinatus bursa which may communicate with joint cavity.

Blood Supply:

- Anterior circumflex humeral vessels.
- Posterior circumflex humeral vessels.
- Suprascapular vessels.
- Subscapular vessels.

Nerve Supply:

- Axillary nerve.
- Musculocutaneous nerve.
- Suprascapular nerve.

Movements of Shoulder Joint:

- Flexion and extension.
- Abduction and adduction.
- Medial and lateral rotation.
- Circumduction.

Figure 3. Movements of shoulder joint(28).

Joint Stability:

The glenohumeral joint is created when the big humeral head articulates with a small glenoid cavity. This joint increases shoulder movement, but it also causes inherent instability. The glenoid labrum, fibrous capsule, ligaments, and muscles all contribute to stabilise the joint. The glenoid labrum stabilises the joint and deepens the glenoid fossa. Ligaments acts as a static structure and provides stability in certain positions.

Muscles of the joint: The fibrous capsule is supplied with fibres by the supraspinatus, infraspinatus, subscapularis, and teres minor tendon of the rotator cuff. By providing the joint with strong lateral support and maintaining appropriate glenohumeral alignment, rotator cuff tendons lower the risk of lateral translocation and increase joint stability. Additional muscles that originate from the supraglenoid tubercle provide the inferior and superior joint support, respectively. These muscles include the long head of the triceps tendon and the long of the biceps tendon. Of the glenohumeral joint, the inferior side is the most unstable and prone to dislocation.

Figure 4. After the proximal end of the humerus, which is stabilising the joint, is removed, a lateral view of the right glenohumeral joint and the surrounding muscles and ligaments.(29)

NORMAL IMAGING ANATOMY

OF SHOULDER JOINT

X-ray of Shoulder Joint:

Figure 5. AP view of X-Ray shoulder. GT- Greater Tubercle; LT- Lesser Tubercle.

CROSS-SECTIONAL IMAGES OF SHOULDER ANATOMY

The anatomy of shoulder can be described by the cross-sectional imaging in four planes often obtained with MRI and they are:

1. Axial.
2. Coronal oblique.
3. Sagittal oblique.
4. Abduction, external rotation (ABER).

Axial:

Figure 6. A to F, MRI axial views of shoulder. 1) acromion, 2) clavicle, 3) acromio-clavicular joint, 4) supraspinatus muscle, 5) anterior main tendons, 6) posterior tendon slip, 7) humeral head, 8) deltoid muscle, 9) scapular spine, 10) coracoid process, 11) glenoid, 12) infraspinatus muscle/tendon, 13) superior glenohumeral ligament, 14) superior labrum, 15) posterior capsule, 16) anterior labrum, 17) posterior labrum, 18) glenoid articular cartilage, 19) greater tuberosity, 20) lesser tuberosity, 21) bicipital groove, 22) middle glenohumeral ligament, 23) bicipital tendon, 24) subscapularis muscle and tendon, 25) inferior labrum(30).

Coronal oblique:

Figure 7. A - D, MRI coronal oblique vies of shoulder. 1) subscapularis muscle, 2) coracoid process, 3) axillary vessels, 4) clavicle, 5) deltoid, 6) supraglenoid fossa, 7) greater tuberosity, 8) bicipital tendon, 9) glenoid cartilage, 10) acromion, 11) humeral articular cartilage, 12) supraspinatus muscle and tendon, 13) superior labrum, 14) inferior labrum, 15) inferior glenohumeral ligament/ axillary recess, 16) infraspinatus muscle/tendon(31).

Sagittal Oblique

Figure 8. A – F, MRI sagittal oblique views of the shoulder. 1) rotator cuff, 2) humeral head, 3) deltoid muscle, 4) subscapularis, 5) bicipital tendon, 6) supraspinatus, 7) infraspinatus, 8) teres minor, 9) acromion, 10) coracoid process, 11) clavicle, 12) scapular spine (root of acromion). AL- anterior labrum, I- inferior glenohumeral ligament, IL- inferior labrum, M- middle glenohumeral ligament, PL- posterior labrum, S- superior glenohumeral ligament(32).

Abduction, external rotation (ABER) oblique views

Figure 9. A-F MRI abduction, external rotation (ABER) oblique axial views of the shoulder. 1) humeral shaft, 2) humeral epiphysis, 3) glenoid, 4) redundant posterior capsule, 5) taut anterior capsule, 6) anterior humeral cortex, 7) anterior labrum, 8) posterior labrum, 9) posterior rotator cuff, 10) inferior glenohumeral ligament, 11) biceps tendon, long head, 12) coracoid process(33).

ULTRASOUND OF ROTATOR CUFF

Figure 10. A) Short axis and long axis of biceps tendon, the arrows depict the biceps tendon. B) Long axis of subscapularis tendon. C) Long axis of supraspinatus tendon. D) Extended field of showing infraspinatus and supraspinatus tendon. E) Acromio-clavicular joint.

CLINICAL EVALUATION OF

ROTATOR CUFF TEAR

The patient's age is crucial when considering a rotator cuff tear as people age, the condition becomes more common and tendon degeneration makes tears more common around age of 40 years. The tear is rare in those under 40 years and most frequently happens in situations like acute trauma and sports-related injuries(34).

The most typical complaints regarding rotator cuff injuries were impingement, pain during the night, arc of pain, and weakness in the abduction and external rotation.

The most helpful indicators for rotator cuff issues were impingement, weakness of the supraspinatus, and weakness of external rotation, according to Murrell and Walton's study, which examined 23 clinical tests. The patient has a 98% chance of having a partial or full thickness tear if they meet two of the three requirements and are at least 60 years old.

Similarly, a different study by Litaker et al(35) revealed that the existence of partial or full-thickness rotator cuff tears was best predicted by patients' age of at least 65years, weakness of external rotation and night pain. The clinical

findings that these authors found most helpful were the arc of discomfort, impingement, and weakness of external rotation. There were differences in the sensitivity and positive predictive value of 76% and 79%, 88% and 70%, 64% and 78%, 97% and 67%, 98 and 67% for weakness of external rotation, nocturnal pain, weakness of abduction, impingement, and arc of pain, respectively(36).

Supraspinatus Evaluation:

Abduction test:

Following arm straightening, the patient's arm is abducted by 20 degrees. The next task is to ask the patient abduct their arm while resisting an outside force.

Figure 11. A clinical image demonstrating the assessment of supraspinatus muscle weakness. The patient is asked to abduct the arm (in an arrow) against applied assistance while maintaining a straight elbow and 20 degrees of abduction(37).

Empty can/ Jobe /full can test: In the scapular plane, the arm is raised to a ninety-degree angle. The arm rotated externally to 45 degrees with the palm facing up in the full can position and then internally rotated fully with the thumb pointing down in the empty can position as shown in figure 12.

Empty Can Test

Figure 12. Illustrating empty can test(38).

Infraspinatus and Teres Minor:

External rotation weakness test: The patient is positioned with the elbow flexed 90 degrees and the shoulder internally rotated 20 degrees. The patient is then asked to resist an inward force.

Figure 13. A clinical image demonstrating weakness in external rotation. The patient has an internal rotation of 20 degrees and a 90-degree flexion of the elbow. Next, the examiner asks the patient to resist an internal force by placing their hand outside of their wrist(39).

Subscapularis:

Lift off test: The patient's arm is passively placed behind their back with their palm facing out during the entire test. There is an obvious subscapularis tear

when the patient is unable to push off against the examiner's palm or when the hand and forearm are not kept off the back.

Figure 14. Clinical photograph showing evaluation of subscapularis tear. With the palm pointing outward, the patient's arm is passively positioned behind their back. Next, the patient is instructed to push against resistance or raise the hand away from the back(40).

Subacromial impingement or rotator cuff disorder test:

Painful arc test:

Figure 15. Demonstrating painful arc test in which patient has pain from 60 to 120 degrees and no pain from neither 0 to 60 degrees nor from 120 to 180 degree(41).

Clinical Examination

<u>Muscles</u>	<u>Clinical Tests</u>
Supraspinatus	Abduction test Jobe test
Infraspinatus and Teres Minor	External weakness test
Subscapularis	Lift off test
Subacromial impingement/ rotator cuff disorder	Painful arc test

Table 1. Clinical examination for rotator cuff disorders/ tears.

ROTATOR CUFF TEARS IMAGING

When a patient comes to orthopaedics department with impingement-related shoulder pain, such as rotator cuff disease, acromial spurs, subacromial-subdeltoid bursitis, coraco-acromial thickening, and acromioclavicular joint invasion. The diagnosis of impingement may typically be made by a skilled practitioner; although, the possible contributing variables may be clearly shown radiologically(42). Shoulder instability and secondary rotator cuff disease may co-occur in patients under 40 years of age. Findings of a normal rotator cuff with MRI or ultrasonography may help rule out rotator cuff illness in the event that the diagnosis is not obvious.

When imaging the rotator cuff the radiologist in mind must clinically implement and strive to achieve the following goals:

1. Determine and assess rotator cuff lesions that may impair the function of the shoulder joint while taking functional anatomy into account.
2. Identify imaging results that improve the functional-anatomic outcome following rotator cuff surgery.
3. List the imaging results and provide a description so that the orthopaedic specialist can choose the best repair method.

The imaging modalities for evaluation of rotator cuff diseases are:

1. Radiography.
2. Arthrography.
3. Ultrasound.
4. CT arthrography.
5. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI).
6. MR arthrography (MRA).
7. Arthroscopy.

Radiography:

In acute rotator cuff tears the radiography may be not significant.

In chronic rotator cuff tears the following features may be present:

- Decreased acromio-humeral interval ($< 7\text{mm}$ in true AP view of shoulder and $< 2\text{mm}$ in active abduction in acute tear).
- Occasionally show supraspinatus opacity and decreased mass as a result of fatty atrophy in chronic tears.
- Chronic tears may show superior humeral subluxation.
- Observations of subacromial impingement include the following: type III acromion, acromion with an inferolateral tilt observed on outlet view (i.e., modified Y view), and formation of a spur on the undersurface of the acromioclavicular joint.

- Subchondral cysts, osteolysis, sclerosis, and notching or pitting of the greater tuberosity are examples of secondary degenerative changes.

Figure 16 A) Prolonged rotator cuff tear where the AP radiograph shows a reduced acromio-humeral distance and a high riding humerus (black arrows). Secondary cuff arthropathy has also been noted; this manifests as sclerosis and faceting in the inferolateral portion of the acromion and the superior aspect of the greater tuberosity (). Also take note of the osteophytosis that originates from the humerus. B) Supraspinatus outlet view showing the normal supraspinatus muscle, which has a homogenous appearance with bulging superior contour (solid arrow) and associated with type III acromial arch that is hooked (open arrow)(43).*

Contrast arthrography:

Contrast arthrography is used to rule out the diagnosis of a rotator cuff tear. The presence of contrast in the subacromial and subdeltoid bursa indicates tear as the bursas do not communicate with the rotator cuff(44). The limitation of contrast arthrography is its invasive nature and lack of soft tissue characterisation(44).

Figure 17. Uniform distension of the joint capsule with distension of superior and inferior recess as marked by arrow. Contrast leak is noted into the subacromial and subdeltoid bursa as marked by () (45).*

CT Arthrography:

A sensitive diagnostic method for rotator cuff injuries is CT arthrography. The sensitivity and specificity of CT arthrography were found to be 99% and 100% for the diagnosis of supraspinatus tears, 97.4% and 99.5% for infraspinatus, and 64.7% and 98.17% for subscapularis tears in a study by Charousset C. et al. that involved the examination of 259 shoulders. The ability of CT arthrography to identify rotator cuff issues has greatly improved as more advanced CT scanners are developed (46). The disadvantages of CT arthrography are its radiation exposure and invasiveness.

Imaging of Rotator Cuff

Figure 18. Complete tear of supraspinatus with contrast extravasating into subdeltoid and subacromial bursa.

Ultrasound:

“Rotator cuff dysfunction can either occur due to tear or tendon degeneration and is the most common cause for referral for evaluation of shoulder”(47).

Likewise, the rotator cuff disease is the most common cause to do ultrasound shoulder.

The rotator cuff tears are classified into:

- Full thickness tear.
- Partial thickness tear.

Full-thickness tear:

When diagnosing rotator cuff tears, ultrasound is a dependable technique that possesses both sensitivity and specificity over 90%(48)(49)(50)(51)(52)(53) for full-thickness tears, and lower interobserver variability(54)(55). Full thickness tears appear as a hypoechoic or anechoic gap within the rotator cuff and have a concave shape at the bursal surface (Fig.19). A severely retracted tear may prevent the rotator cuff tendon from being seen. A full thickness tear may show hypoechoic fluid, echogenic debris, or granulation tissue which fills the space between the retracted tendon end and greater tuberosity.

Figure 19. A) schematic diagram of complete supraspinatus tear B) hypoechoic or anechoic gap within supraspinatus tendon suggestive of complete tear of supraspinatus.

“Small foci of debris within the tear gap may give the appearance of mobile or “floating” bright spots”(53). The enhanced transmission of the ultrasonic beam due to the fluid inside the tear gap may make the underlying humeral head articular cartilage easier to see; this is referred to as the "cartilage interface sign"(36). A partial tear or full thickness tear which show granulation tissue and debris can occasionally be identified by an irregular echotexture near the supraspinatus muscle. This uncertainty may be resolved by dynamic compression of the aberrant location, which causes debris and complicated fluid to whirl inside the rotator cuff tear.

Acute vs chronic full-thickness tear:

<u>Acute full-thickness tear</u>	<u>Chronic full-thickness tear</u>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Glenohumeral and bursal effusion is more common. • Mid-substance tear, medial to the bone-tendon junction are more likely to be acute tears. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Glenohumeral and bursal effusion is less common. • Severely retracted tears are more likely chronic tears and the tendon gap may be filled with non-compressible, complex echogenic debris and granulation tissue that are contiguous with subacromial and subdeltoid bursa.

Table 2. Difference between acute and chronic full thickness tear of supraspinatus.

Partial thickness tear:

Any age of patient may experience partial thickness tears. Young athletes are more likely than older patients to experience partial tears, which are more common than full thickness tears in this age group. When a patient ages, the supraspinatus tendon is more likely to experience partial thickness tears as a result of tendon degeneration.

“Partial thickness tears are characterized by focal area of hypoechogenicity or mixed echogenicity involving one side of the tendon, but not extending through the entire thickness(Fig. 20)”(52).

Types of partial thickness tear:

Bursal surface tear: Superficially occurs in the supraspinatus tendon fibres, a short distance below the subacromial-subdeltoid bursa. Young adults most frequently experience this type of partial thickness tear(56).

Articular sided tears: At the tendon's subsurface where it meets the joint space.

Intrasubstance tears: Axially within the tendon fibres or longitudinally within the tendon footprint substance at the enthesis.

Rim rent tears: A specific type of partial thickness tear that originates at the articular side of the supraspinatus tendon and spreads into the tendon foot print on the greater tuberosity in athletes who toss objects overhead.

Imaging of Rotator Cuff

Figure 20. A) schematic diagram of partial thickness tear; B) A focal area of hypoechoogenicity present in the bursal side of supraspinatus which is suggestive of bursal sides supraspinatus tear.

Grading of Partial thickness tears:

Grade I: < 25% thickness(-3mm).

Grade II: <25% - 50%(3-6mm).

Grade III: >50%(+6mm).

Classification of Partial Tears based on depth of defect

	Articular surface	Bursal surface
Grade 1 <25% thickness (-3 mm)		
Grade 2 <25%-50% thickness (3-6 mm)		
Grade 3 >50% thickness (+6 mm)		

Fig 21. Illustration of Partial Tear Subtypes(57).

Advantages of ultrasound:

- Accurate, well tolerated and cost-effective technique.
- Ultrasound is a good alternative technique in claustrophobic, large side patients and in patients who have implanted metallic and electronic devices.
- Patient imaging during painful or clicking movements is made possible by the use of ultrasound, which allows for the dynamic assessment of the rotator cuff.
- Better in diagnosing calcium deposits within the tendon when compared to MRI.

Limitations:

- Its drawback is usually seen as operator reliant and having a lengthy learning curve, particularly when partial thickness tears are present and the interobserver variability is higher.
- Patients with substantial restrictions on shoulder movement and those who are obese have an impact on the sensitivity of ultrasound imaging.
- Cannot detect glenoid labral injuries and bony disorders.

MRI SHOULDER

The spectrum between partial and full thickness tears, as well as rotator cuff degeneration/tendinopathy, can be depicted on an MRI.

On PD images, intrinsic cuff degeneration/tendinopathy exhibits elevated signal intensity in the distal tendon; on T2 weighted images, this finding is still present but does not intensify.

“The sensitivities for imaging of full thickness rotator cuff tears have ranged from 80 to 100 % and specificities from 94% to 100%”(58)(59)(60)(61). For diagnosing partial thickness tears on nonarthrogram MRI is more problematic with sensitivities upto 92% and specificities of 83% to 100%. The use of 3-tesla(3T) MRI was reported by Magee and Williams, achieving a sensitivity of 98% and specificity of 96%(62).

Partial-thickness tears:

Partial tears appear as focal areas of increased signal intensity on short echo-times on MRI; these areas also increase signal intensity on long TE images, though they do not necessarily match the signal intensity of joint fluid (Fig 22).

In the atypical regions the signals do not penetrate the complete thickness of the tendon.

Figure 22. Abnormal high signal intensity in the PDFS sequence for the supraspinatus tendon, involving the articular surface fibres, which suggests a partial tear.

Fluid is observed in the glenohumeral joint in the articular surface partial thickness tear. Within the subacromial-subdeltoid bursa, there may be a bursal side tear. Tendon delamination is caused by an articular rim rent tear that extends along the tendon fibres at greater tuberosity. Partial-thickness rips can be identified by partial cuff fibre retraction.

Synder classification of partial rotator cuff tears are as

follow(63):

- 0- Normal.
- 1- Minimal superficial bursal or synovial irritation or mild capsular fraying in a small localized area (< 1cm).
- 2- Fraying and failure of some rotator cuff fibers with synovial bursa or capsular injury (< 2cm).
- 3- Fraying and fragmentation of tendon fibers usually involving the whole surface of a cuff tendon, most commonly supraspinatus (< 3cm).
- 4- Severe tear with tendon fraying, fragmentation and a sizable flap tear involving more than single tendon.

Depending on depth of tendon fiber the partial tear can be graded

as(61):

- 1: less than 3mm deep.
- 2: 3 to 6mm deep and less than 50% of the cuff thickness involved.
- 3: High-grade partial thickness tear > 6mm deep with more than 50% of rotator cuff thickness involved.

Full-thickness tears:

On at least one image, there is an abnormal focus of increased T2 weighted signal intensity that interrupts the tendon throughout its entire superior-to-inferior extent (fig 23). Full thickness tears are frequently associated with fluid in the subacromial-subdeltoid bursa. Occasionally, the tendon gap is filled with scar tissue, or there may be insufficient fluid in the joint. Tendon retraction and atrophy of the affected muscle with fatty infiltration are additional helpful indicators. Fat infiltration is primarily visible on T1 weighted images and is more common in chronic tears.

Figure 23. Abnormal area of signal intensity of the supraspinatus tendon completely extending superior-inferiorly on PDFS sequence- suggestive of complete tear.

Pitfalls for diagnosing rotator cuff tear on MRI:

- **Magic angle artifact:** Increased signal intensity on T1 weighted image in which an artifactual focus of increased signal intensity may occur on short TE images of tendon oriented 55 degrees to the constant magnetic field which was described by Erickson and co-workers(64).
- The radiologist must be aware of previous injection therapy as there will be increased T2 signal intensity can occur in the subacromial space which can be misread for tear(65).
- Another discrepancy between surgical findings and MRI occurs in interstitial tear of tendons that does not extend to surface. Because there is no surface communication, arthroscopy may not reveal a tear(66).

MR Arthrography:

“MR arthrography has a sensitivity, specificity and accuracy of 96%, 99% and 98% respectively for full thickness tears”(67). “For partial thickness tears, it has as sensitivity, specificity and accuracy of 80%, 97% and 95% respectively(68)(69). Because non-arthrographic MRI of shoulder has a higher degree of accuracy, particularly for full-thickness tears, any substantial gain in accuracy with MR arthrography is in the diagnosis of partial thickness tears”(70).

METHODOLOGY

Type of study:

- Hospital based prospective study.

Study design:

- **Study period:** September 2022- June 2024.
- **Study conducted:** Shri BM Patil Medical College and Research Centre.

Study population:

Patients visiting department of Orthopaedics “With clinical symptoms of rotator cuff tears(Pain and malfunction) subjected to Ultrasound and MRI shoulder” at B.L.D.E Shri B.M .Patil Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura.

Criteria for selection of cases:

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patient with clinical symptoms of rotator cuff tears and sent to ultrasound and MRI shoulder.
- Patient > 18 years.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients with contraindications to MRI.
- On plain radiography, patients with known or diagnosed fracture/dislocation involving the shoulder.
- Patients who had undergone shoulder surgery for any reason for rotator cuff.

Method of collection of data:

- Informed written consent.
- Detailed history.
- Brief physical examination.
- Imaging of the participant.

Material and Methods:**Machine:**

- Ultrasonography (**GE Voluson S8**) of the shoulder is done using **with 09 MHz linear-array transducer.**
- MRI shoulder is done using **using GE Signa Explorer of 1.5 Tesla.**

Methods:**Ultrasound Shoulder:****Scan Technique:**

Ultrasound protocol: A standard protocol is established for performing ultrasound shoulder for an accurate and consistent diagnosis of shoulder pathology as described in Table 3.

Structures	Ultrasound protocol
Long head of biceps tendon	Long and short-axis static images.
Subscapularis tendon	Long and shot axis static images. Dynamic evaluation for sub-coracoid impingement.
Supraspinatus tendon	Long and short axis static images. Dynamic evaluation for subacromial impingement
Infraspinatus tendon	Long and short axis static images.
Teres minor tendon	Long and short axis static images
Supraspinatus and infraspinatus muscles	Sagittal images- panorama if possible
Posterior shoulder	Axial plane image.
Acromioclavicular joint	Coronal plane image.

Table 3. Depicting routine shoulder ultrasound protocol.

Patient and sonographer position:

Ideally, the patient should be sitting up straight, either on a revolving stool or the side of a bed. The positioning of the patient would be hampered by using a chair with a backrest. In order to hold their arm in an ergonomic and neutral position, sonographers should also sit on rotating stools that are higher than their patients. The back rest is taken out of the patient's wheelchair for a short while. A more limited scan is performed on a supine patient with the afflicted shoulder resting on the edge of the bed in the event that the patient is unable to sit.

Subscapularis tendon evaluation:

The subscapularis is evaluated when the patient's arm is at the side, externally rotated, and palm facing upwards (Fig. 10.A). The subscapularis tendon is examined in the long axis (Fig. 10.B) with the probe aligned along the subscapularis tendon and in the short axis with the probe perpendicular to it. Finding the subscapularis tendon can be aided by palpating the coracoid process of the scapula, which is palpable in many patients and serves as a significant anatomic landmark. It is important to distinguish between normal hypoechoic muscle and fluid. The patient's arm can be rotated from the external to the neutral position in this posture, allowing one to assess for sub-coracoid impingement by watching the passing of tendon fibers deep to the coracoid process. Dynamic

maneuver is also useful to assess for long head biceps tendon subluxation from the bicipital groove.

Figure 10. A) Positioning the patient to assess the subscapularis tendon using US. The black box, or tendon, is moved more anteriorly by the external rotation of the arm. B) Tilted transversely to the arm, but orientated longitudinally to the tendon of the subscapularis (shaded box)(71).

Supraspinatus evaluation:

In the neutral position the supraspinatus tendon is largely obscured due to overlying acromion. To withdraw the tendon out of the acromion there are two methods to performed which are:

- **Crass position:** Request that the patient to put their hand behind their back and use their back to reach towards the back pocket on the other side. This causes the shoulder to flex, rotate internally, and adduct.

- **Modified crass position:** For individuals who have shoulder pain, the crass position can be challenging. The elbow is fixed and pointed posteriorly when using this technique, which places the palm of the hand on the ipsilateral hip or buttock (Fig 11.A).

Figure 11. A) Modified Crass position: Positioning the patient to allow ultrasound assessment of the supraspinatus tendon. The supraspinatus tendon (shaded box) insertion site (i) on the superior aspect of the greater tuberosity is located beneath the acromion when the elbow is pointing backward and the hand is placed on the buttock as it is. B) Placing the ultrasound transducer in front of the acromioclavicular joint and roughly parallel to the scapula's spine (black line on top of the shoulder), allows for a longitudinal evaluation of the supraspinatus tendon (shaded box). C) Transducer location (box) for transverse evaluation of the supraspinatus tendon. D) The transducer is situated in the supraspinatus fossa, anteriorly and parallel to the scapular spine (black line)(71).

To see the supraspinatus in long axis, the probe should be positioned parallel to the tendon's long axis orientation. This will cause the probe to be positioned obliquely in the sagittal plane with respect to the patient, pointing in the direction of the patient's ear (Fig 11.B). The long head of the biceps tendon in long axis can be used as a landmark to help locate the tendon's most anterior portion. The entire supraspinatus muscle is visible if the long axis probe is moved posteriorly. At its insertion, or "footprint," the normal supraspinatus muscle has a smooth, echogenic fibrillar tapering that is commonly referred to as having a "bird beak appearance".

The tendon is then imaged along its short axis by rotating the probe 90 degrees (Fig 11.C). In this position, the more cord-like anterior of the supraspinatus tendon combines with the flatter quadrilateral mid and posterior fibers.

For supraspinatus subacromial impingement, a dynamic evaluation can now be performed. The greater tuberosity is positioned laterally and the acromion is at the medial aspect of the field of view when the probe is placed in the coronal plane with the patient's arm in a neutral position by his or her side. The supraspinatus tendon's motion beneath the acromion is then seen as the patient slowly abducts their arm. Without tendon deformation under the acromion, bursa deformation, or bursal fluid pooling, the tendon should move smoothly and continuously.

Infraspinatus, teres minor and posterior shoulder evaluation:

The patient can be placed in the modified Crass position or with the arm hanging at the side for simple posterior scanning in both the long and short axis from the supraspinatus.

The patient may also be asked to bring their arm forward across their chest and place their hand on their opposite shoulder in an alternate position. The probe is held in an oblique transverse orientation and placed on the posterior shoulder to parallel the long axis of the infraspinatus tendon; the tendon and muscle are then assessed after the probe is turned 90 degrees to the short axis of the infraspinatus.

The normal muscle is hypoechoic and located in the infraspinatus fossa, below the scapular spine.

Upon examination in this orientation, the teres minor tendon is observed to insert inferiorly to the infraspinatus tendon at the posterior aspect of the greater tuberosity.

The evaluation of the posterior aspect shoulder involves the visualization of glenohumeral joint fluid, with limited visualization of the posterior labrum and spino-glenoid notch. (Fig 12).

Figure 12. Posterior evaluation of shoulder(71).

MRI Shoulder:

Scan Technique:

- **Positioning of patient:** Supine.
- **Type of coil:** Surface body coil.

- **MRI shoulder protocol:**

<u>Sequences</u>	<u>Slice Thickness</u>	<u>TR/TE (msec)</u>	<u>Field of view(mm)</u>
Ax PDFS	4	2360/ 30	160 X 160
Ax T2* Merge	4	538/ 7.2	160 X 160
Cor T2	4	3068/ 65	160 X 160
Cor T1	4	432	160 X 160
Cor PDFS	4	2143/ 30	160 X 160
Sag PDFS	4	2331/40	160 x 160

Table 4. MRI shoulder protocol

Cost of Study:

MRI shoulder: $53 \times 4000 = 2,12,000$ Rs.

Ultrasound shoulder: $53 \times 415 = 21,995$ Rs.

Total cost: **2,33,995 Rs.**

SAMPLE SIZE CALCULATION

SAMPLE SIZE:

The software G*Power ver. 3.1.9.4 is being used to calculate the sample size. The accuracy of partial thickness rotator cuff tears is 83%, and 53 samples are needed for this study. In order to detect a difference in Proportion (Exact – Proportion: Difference from constant) with a 5% significance level, a power of 99% must be attained (binomial test, one sample case).

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

Once the data is entered into a Microsoft Excel sheet, statistical analyses are carried out using the statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) (Version 20). Graphs, counts, percentages, mean, and standard deviation are used to display the findings. An independent sample t-test will be employed to compare the differences between the two groups in continuously distributed normally distributed variables. For variables that are not normally distributed, the Mann-Whitney U test is employed. The Fisher's exact test or the Chi-square test are used to compare categorical variables between the two groups. If $p < 0.05$ is considered statistically significant. Every statistical analysis is done using two tails.

OBSERVATION

EPIDEMIOLOGY

Age distribution:

In our data the involvement of rotator cuff was more common in the middle age group and the age wise distribution of the population is described as below in the Table 1 and Figure 13.

<u>Age(Years)</u>	<u>No. of patients</u>	<u>Percentage(%)</u>
< 20	1	1.9
20 – 29	4	7.5
30 – 39	5	9.4
40 – 49	15	28.3
50 – 59	17	32.1
60+	11	20.8
Total	53	100.0

Table 5. Depicting age wise distribution of rotator cuff tears.

Figure 13. Bar-diagram of age wise distribution of for involvement of rotator cuff tears.

Gender Distribution:

In our study the rotator cuff was more involved in males than females as described in the Table 2 and Figure 14.

<u>Gender</u>	<u>No of patients</u>	<u>Percentage(%)</u>
Male	35	66.0
Female	18	34.0
Total	53	100

Table 6. Gender wise distribution of rotator cuff tear

Figure 14. Pie-chart of gender wise distribution of rotator cuff tear.

Side wise distribution:

The side which is most involved in our data was right shoulder as shown Table 3 and Figure 15.

<u>Side</u>	<u>No of patients</u>	<u>Percentage (%)</u>
Right	38	71.7
Left	15	28.3
Total	53	100

Table 7. Depicting the side of shoulder involvement in rotator cuff tear

Figure 15. Pie chart of more common side of shoulder involvement in rotator cuff tears.

HISTORY:

The most common complaint given by the patients was shoulder pain as described in Table 8 and Figure 16.

<u>COMPLAINTS</u>	<u>FREQUENCY</u>	<u>VALID PERCENT</u>
SHOULDER PAIN	52	98%
RESTRICTION OF MOVEMENTS	42	79%
TRAUMA	20	37%

Table 8. Frequency of complaints.

Figure 16. Bar-diagram of more common symptom in rotator cuff tears.

ROTATOR CUFF IMAGING FINDING:**ROTATOR CUFF TEARS FINDING ON ULTRASOUND**

In our study the rotator cuff tears were present in 69.8% out of the total no of subjects and 30.2% depicted no tear on ultrasound as shown in the Table 9.

		<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Percent</u>	<u>Valid Percent</u>	<u>Cumulative Percent</u>
Valid	Yes	37	69.8	69.8	100.0
	No	16	30.2	30.2	30.2
	Total	53	100.0	100.0	

Table 9. Results of rotator cuff tear on ultrasound.

ROTATOR CUFF TEARS FINDING ON MRI

In this study of the rotator cuff tears were present in 69.8% out of the total no of subjects and 30.2% depicted no tear on MRI as shown in the Table 10.

		<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Percent</u>	<u>Valid Percent</u>	<u>Cumulative Percent</u>
Valid	Yes	37	69.8	69.8	100.0
	No	16	30.2	30.2	30.2
	Total	53	100.0	100.0	

Table 10. Results of rotator cuff tear on MRI.

SUPRASPINATUS TEAR FINDINGS ON ULTRASOUND

In our study the supraspinatus tears were present in 62.3% out of the total no of subjects and 37.7% depicted no tear on ultrasound as shown in the Table 11.

		<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Percent</u>	<u>Valid Percent</u>	<u>Cumulative Percent</u>
Valid	Yes	33	62.3	62.3	100.0
	No	20	37.7	37.7	37.7
	Total	53	100.0	100.0	

Table 11. Results of supraspinatus tear on ultrasound.

SUPRASPINATUS TEAR FINDINGS ON MRI

In our study the supraspinatus tears were present in 62.3% out of the total no of subjects and 37.7% depicted no tear on MRI as shown in the Table 12.

		<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Percent</u>	<u>Valid Percent</u>	<u>Cumulative Percent</u>
Valid	Yes	33	62.3	62.3	100.0
	No	20	37.7	37.7	37.7
	Total	53	100.0	100.0	

Table 12. Results of supraspinatus tear on MRI.

SUPRASPINATUS PARTIAL TEAR FINDINGS ON ULTRASOUND

In our study the supraspinatus partial thickness tears were present in 49.1% out of the total no of subjects and 50.9% depicted no tear on ultrasound as shown in the Table 13.

		<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Percent</u>	<u>Valid Percent</u>	<u>Cumulative Percent</u>
Valid	Yes	26	49.1	49.1	100.0
	No	27	50.9	50.9	50.9
	Total	53	100.0	100.0	

Table 13. Results of supraspinatus partial tear on ultrasound.

SUPRASPINATUS PARTIAL TEAR FINDINGS ON MRI

In our study the supraspinatus partial thickness tears were present in 49.1% out of the total no of subjects and 50.9% depicted no tear on ultrasound as shown in the Table 14.

		<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Percent</u>	<u>Valid Percent</u>	<u>Cumulative Percent</u>
Valid	Yes	26	49.1	49.1	100.0
	No	27	50.9	50.9	50.9
	Total	53	100.0	100.0	

Table 14. Results of supraspinatus partial tear on MRI.

**SUPRASPINATUS FULL THICKNESS TEAR FINDINGS ON
ULTRASOUND**

In our study the supraspinatus full thickness tears were present in 17% out of the total no of subjects and 83% depicted no tear on ultrasound as shown in the Table 15.

		<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Percent</u>	<u>Valid Percent</u>	<u>Cumulative Percent</u>
Valid	Yes	9	17.0	17.0	100.0
	No	44	83.0	83.0	83.0
	Total	53	100.0	100.0	

Table 15. Results of supraspinatus full-thickness tear on ultrasound.

SUPRASPINATUS FULL THICKNESS TEAR FINDINGS ON MRI

In our study the supraspinatus full thickness tears were present in 18.9% out of the total no of subjects and 83% depicted no tear on ultrasound as shown in the Table 16.

		<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Percent</u>	<u>Valid Percent</u>	<u>Cumulative Percent</u>
Valid	Yes	9	17	17	100.0
	No	44	83	83.0	83.0
	Total	53	100.0	100.0	

Table 16. Results of supraspinatus full-thickness tear on MRI.

OTHERS: SUBSCAPULARIS, INFRASPINATUS AND TERES MINOR**FINDINGS ON ULTRASOUND**

In our study the other muscle tears of subscapularis, infraspinatus and teres minor were present in 28.3% out of the total no of subjects and 71.7% depicted no tear on ultrasound as shown in the Table 17.

		<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Percent</u>	<u>Valid Percent</u>	<u>Cumulative Percent</u>
Valid	Yes	15	28.3	28.3	100.0
	No	38	71.7	71.7	71.7
	Total	53	100.0	100.0	

Table 17. Results of subscapularis, infraspinatus and teres minor tear on ultrasound.

OTHERS: SUBSCAPULARIS, INFRASPINATUS AND TERES MINOR**FINDINGS ON MRI**

In our study the other muscle tears of subscapularis, infraspinatus and teres minor were present in 20.8% out of the total no of subjects and 79.2% depicted no tear on ultrasound as shown in the Table 18.

		<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Percent</u>	<u>Valid Percent</u>	<u>Cumulative Percent</u>
Valid	Yes	11	20.8	20.8	100.0
	No	42	79.2	79.2	79.2
	Total	53	100.0	100.0	

Table 18 Results of subscapularis, infraspinatus and teres minor tear on MRI.

ULTRASOUND AND MRI CORRELATION OF ROTATOR CUFF**TEARS**

The correlation of the rotator cuff tears on ultrasound and MRI was well established with chi square value of 28.3 and significant p-value < 0.05 as described in the table 19.

			<u>Rotator Cuff Tear(MRI)</u>		<u>Total</u>	<u>Chi Square test</u>	<u>Significance value</u>
			<u>No</u>	<u>Yes</u>			
Rotator Cuff Tear(USG)	No	Count	13	3	16	28.354	P=0.001*
		% within Tear (MRI)	81.3%	8.1%	30.2%		
	Yes	Count	3	34	37		
		% within Tear (MRI)	18.8%	91.9%	69.8%		
Total		Count	16	37	53		
		% within Tear (MRI)	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%		

**Statistically Significant*

Table 19. Correlation of ultrasound and MRI of rotator cuff tears.

ULTRASOUND AND MRI CORRELATION OF SUPRASPINATUS**TEAR**

The correlation of the supraspinatus tear on ultrasound and MRI was well established with chi square value of 30.54 and significant p-value < 0.05 as described in the Table 20.

			<u>Supraspinatus Tear(MRI)</u>		<u>Total</u>	<u>Chi Square test</u>	<u>Significance value</u>
			<u>No</u>	<u>Yes</u>			
Supraspinatus Tear (USG)	<u>No</u>	Count	17	3	20	30.540	P=0.001*
		% within Supraspinatus Tear (MRI)	85.0%	9.1%	37.7%		
	<u>Yes</u>	Count	3	30	33		
		% within Supraspinatus Tear(MRI)	15.0%	90.9%	62.3%		
Total		Count	20	33	53		
		% within Supraspinatus Tear (MRI)	100.0 %	100.0%	100.0%		
<u>*Statistically Significant</u>							

Table 20. showing correlation of Ultrasound and MRI of supraspinatus tear.

**ULTRASOUND AND MRI CORRELATION OF SUPRASPINATUS
PARTIAL TEAR**

The correlation of the supraspinatus partial-thickness tears on ultrasound and MRI was well established with chi square value of 31.71 and significant p-value < 0.05 as described in the Table 21.

			<u>Supraspinatus Partial thickness (MRI)</u>		<u>Total</u>	<u>Chi Square test</u>	<u>Significance value</u>
			<u>No</u>	<u>Yes</u>			
Supraspinatus Partial thickness(USG)	<u>No</u>	Count	24	3	27	31.710	P=0.0012*
		% within Supraspinatus Partial thickness(MRI)	88.9%	11.5%	50.9%		
	<u>Yes</u>	Count	3	23	26		
		% within Supraspinatus Partial thickness(MRI)	11.1%	88.5%	49.1%		
Total		Count	27	26	53		
		% within Supraspinatus Partial thickness(MRI)	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%		
<u>*Statistically Significant</u>							

Table 21. Correlation between ultrasound and MRI of supraspinatus partial-thickness tears.

**ULTRASOUND AND MRI CORRELATION OF SUPRASPINATUS
FULL THICKNESS TEAR**

The correlation of the supraspinatus full-thickness tears on ultrasound and MRI was well established with chi square value of 46.61 and significant p-value < 0.05 as described in the Table 22.

			<u>Supraspinatus Full Thickness(MRI)</u>		<u>Total</u>	<u>Chi Square Test</u>	<u>Significance Value</u>
			No	Yes			
Supraspinatus Full Thickness(USG)	No	Count	43	1	44	46.616	P=0.0021*
		% within Supraspinatus Full Thickness(MRI)	100.0%	10.0 %	83.0%		
	Yes	Count	0	9	9		
		% within Supraspinatus Full Thickness(MRI)	0.0%	90.0 %	17.0%		
Total		Count	43	10	53		
		% within Supraspinatus Full Thickness(MRI)	100.0%	100.0 %	100.0%		
<i><u>*Statistically Significant</u></i>							

Table 22. Correlation between ultrasound and MRI of supraspinatus full-thickness tears.

**ULTRASOUND AND MRI CORRELATION OF OTHER ROTATOR
CUFF MUSCLES -SUBSCAPULARIS, INFRASPINATUS AN TERES
MINOR TEAR**

The correlation of the other rotator c tears on ultrasound and MRI was well established with chi square value of 19.5 and significant p-value < 0.05 as described in the Table 23.

		<u>Others:</u> <u>Infraspinatus, Teres</u> <u>Minor and</u> <u>Subscapularis(MRI)</u>		<u>Total</u>	<u>Chi</u> <u>Square</u> <u>Test</u>	<u>Significance</u> <u>Value</u>
		<u>No</u>	<u>Yes</u>			
<u>Others:</u> <u>Infraspinatus, Teres</u> <u>Minor and</u> <u>Subscapularis(USG)</u>	<u>No</u>	<u>Count</u>	36	2	38	19.592 P=0.004*
		<u>% within Others:</u> <u>Infraspinatus, Teres</u> <u>Minor and</u> <u>Subscapularis(MRI)</u>	85.7%	18.2%	71.7%	
	<u>Yes</u>	<u>Count</u>	6	9	15	
		<u>% within Others:</u> <u>Infraspinatus, Teres</u> <u>Minor and</u> <u>Subscapularis(MRI)</u>	14.3%	81.8%	28.3%	
<u>Total</u>		<u>Count</u>	42	11	53	
		<u>% within Others:</u> <u>Infraspinatus, Teres</u> <u>Minor and</u> <u>Subscapularis(MRI)</u>	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
<i><u>*Statistically Significant</u></i>						

Table 23. Correlation of other rotator cuff muscles on ultrasound and MRI.

RESULTS

In this study of rotator cuff tears, the incidence was more common among the middle age group of subjects between 50-59years and in males. The rotator cuff tears more commonly involved the right shoulder and most commonly, involved muscle was supraspinatus muscle with prevalence of 62.6%. The type of supraspinatus tear involved was most commonly the partial tear with prevalence of 49.0%.

Rotator cuff tears:

With a p-value<0.05, there was a significant overall correlation between the ultrasound and shoulder MRI for rotator cuff tears. According to Table 24, the ultrasound had a 91.8% sensitivity and 81.2% specificity with an accuracy of 88.68% when compared to MRI.

<u>Statistics</u>	<u>Value</u>	<u>95% CI</u>
Sensitivity	91.89%	78.09% to 98.30%
Specificity	81.25%	54.35% to 95.95%
Positive Likelihood Ratio	4.90	1.76 to 13.65
Negative Likelihood Ratio	0.10	0.03 to 0.30
Disease prevalence (*)	69.81%	55.66% to 81.66%
Positive Predictive Value (*)	91.89%	80.27% to 96.93%
Negative Predictive Value (*)	81.25%	58.82% to 92.93%
Accuracy (*)	88.68%	76.97% to 95.73%
<i>(*) These values are dependent on disease prevalence</i>		

Table 24. Diagnostic test for overall rotator cuff tears.

Supraspinatus Tears:

With a significant p-value of less than 0.05, the correlation between the shoulder MRI and ultrasound was well established. Table 25 displays the supraspinatus tear's sensitivity, specificity, and diagnostic accuracy, which were 90.9%, 85%, and 88.6%, respectively.

<u>Statistics</u>	<u>Value</u>	<u>95% CI</u>
Sensitivity	90.91%	75.67% to 98.08%
Specificity	85.00%	62.11% to 96.79%
Positive Likelihood Ratio	6.06	2.12 to 17.30
Negative Likelihood Ratio	0.11	0.04 to 0.32
Disease prevalence (*)	62.26%	47.89% to 75.21%
Positive Predictive Value (*)	90.91%	77.79% to 96.62%
Negative Predictive Value (*)	85.00%	65.48% to 94.42%
Accuracy (*)	88.68%	76.97% to 95.73%
<i>(*) These values are dependent on disease prevalence</i>		

Table 25. Diagnostic test for supraspinatus tears.

The supraspinatus tears were further classified into:

- Full thickness supraspinatus tears.
- Partial thickness supraspinatus tears.

Full-thickness tears of supraspinatus muscle:

With a significant p-value of less than 0.05, a strong correlation was found between the results of shoulder MRI and ultrasound in the diagnosis of full thickness rotator cuff tears. As indicated in Table 26, full-thickness rotator cuff tears had 100% sensitivity, 100% specificity, and 100% accuracy.

Statistic	Value	95% CI
Sensitivity	100.00%	66.37% to 100.00%
Specificity	100.00%	91.96% to 100.00%
Positive Likelihood Ratio		
Negative Likelihood Ratio	0.00	
Disease prevalence (*)	16.98%	8.07% to 29.80%
Positive Predictive Value (*)	100.00%	66.37% to 100.00%
Negative Predictive Value (*)	100.00%	91.96% to 100.00%
Accuracy (*)	100.00%	93.28% to 100.00%
<i>(*) These values are dependent on disease prevalence</i>		

Table 26. Diagnostic tests of supraspinatus full-thickness tears.

Partial thickness tears of supraspinatus muscle:

A well-established correlation was present between ultrasound and MRI shoulder for partial-thickness tears of supraspinatus muscle with a significant p-value of <0.05. The sensitivity was 88.4% and specificity was 88.6% with a diagnostic accuracy of 88.68% as shown in Table 21.

<u>Statistics</u>	<u>Value</u>	<u>95% CI</u>
Sensitivity	88.46%	69.85% to 97.55%
Specificity	88.89%	70.84% to 97.65%
Positive Likelihood Ratio	7.96	2.71 to 23.35
Negative Likelihood Ratio	0.13	0.04 to 0.38
Disease prevalence (*)	49.06%	35.06% to 63.16%
Positive Predictive Value (*)	88.46%	72.33% to 95.74%
Negative Predictive Value (*)	88.89%	73.24% to 95.90%
Accuracy (*)	88.68%	76.97% to 95.73%
<i>(*) These values are dependent on disease prevalence</i>		

Table 27. Diagnostic tests of partial-thickness tears of supraspinatus muscle.

Others- Subscapularis, Infraspinatus and Teres Minor Tears:

The other group of muscles like subscapularis, infraspinatus and teres minor had good correlation on ultrasound and MRI shoulder overall with a significant p-value < 0.05. The prevalence in our study for the other group of rotator cuff muscles were less and the sensitivity, specificity was 81.8 and 85.7% with overall diagnostic accuracy was 84.9% as depicted in Table 28.

<u>Statistics</u>	<u>Value</u>	<u>95% CI</u>
Sensitivity	81.82%	48.22% to 97.72%
Specificity	85.71%	71.46% to 94.57%
Positive Likelihood Ratio	5.73	2.60 to 12.64
Negative Likelihood Ratio	0.21	0.06 to 0.75
Disease prevalence (*)	20.75%	10.84% to 34.11%
Positive Predictive Value (*)	60.00%	40.47% to 76.80%
Negative Predictive Value (*)	94.74%	83.63% to 98.45%
Accuracy (*)	84.91%	72.41% to 93.25%
<i>(*) These values are dependent on disease prevalence</i>		

Table 28. Diagnostic test of other rotator cuff muscles.

ROTATOR CUFF'S TEAR CASES

SUPRASPINATUS MUSCLE

A 67 years old male came with complaints of shoulder pain and difficulty in movement since 3months.

Figure 17. A) A hypoechoic gap is observed along the supraspinatus muscle's articular surface in the right shoulder ultrasound, indicating an articular partial thickness tear. B) A hyperintense signal intensity gap is observed along the articular surface of the supraspinatus muscle in the right shoulder MRI, which reveals an articular partial thickness tear of the muscle.

A 48-year-old female came with complaints of right shoulder pain for 15 days and difficulty in movement of shoulder for 1 week.

Figure 18. A) An irregular hypoechoic gap is observed along the articular surface of the supraspinatus muscle in the right shoulder's ultrasound; B) and C) an MRI of the right shoulder's coronal and sagittal images reveals a conjoint tendon tear of the supraspinatus and infraspinatus muscles.

A 47-year-old female came with history of trauma 20 days back with shoulder pain and difficulty in moving rotating right shoulder.

Figure 19. A) A full-thickness rupture of the supraspinatus tendon is seen on the right shoulder ultrasound. There is also a hypoechoic gap and no visible supraspinatus tendon fibres. B) A full-thickness supraspinatus tendon tear is visible on the right shoulder's coronal MRI images.

A 54-year-old male came with complaints of shoulder pain for 1 month.

Figure 20. A) Ultrasound of left shoulder shows supraspinatus tendinosis- tendon appears bulky with altered echotexture. B) Coronal images of MRI of left shoulder shows supraspinatus tendinosis- tendon appears bulky with altered signal intensity.

SUBSCAPULARIS

**A 42-year-old female came with history of fall and shoulder pain
on left side for 1 day**

Figure 21. A) Ultrasound of left shoulder shows tear of subscapularis. B) Ultrasound of left shoulder shows partial tear of supraspinatus. C) MRI of left shoulder shows partial tear of supraspinatus. D) & E) sagittal and axial images show tear of subscapularis

SUPRASPINATUS, INFRASPINATUS AND TERES MINOR

TEARS

A 36-year-old male came with complaints of trauma to left shoulder 1 day back, shoulder pain and difficulty in movement for 1 day.

Figure 22. A) Ultrasound of left shoulder showing complete tear of supraspinatus muscle B) ultrasound showing tear of infraspinatus muscle C) Coronal image of MRI of left shoulder showing complete tear of the supraspinatus at its insertion to greater tuberosity D) & E) Axial image showing tears of infraspinatus and teres minor.

DISCUSSION

A number of methods, such as a clinical examination, X-ray, arthrography, ultrasound, CT scan and MRI, are used to assess individuals who express shoulder pain. While very specific and sensitive, conventional magnetic resonance imaging cannot be the primary means of inquiry. On the other hand, ultrasound is a useful non-invasive and inexpensive method to diagnose rotator cuff tears. In our study, participants who had a clinical suspicion of rotator cuff tear their ultrasound and MRI findings were compared.

Since each modality has developed over years, it is still challenging to determine which is the best choice, despite the numerous published research comparing the costs and effectiveness of ultrasound versus MRI in evaluating rotator cuff tears. The effectiveness of its diagnostics was enhanced by the availability of high frequency transducers and high resolution sonography equipment. Further improving the diagnostic quality are by recently developed MRI machine and surface coils which are better.

In our hospital based prospective study, of Vijayapura population, the rotator cuff tears comprised a group about 53 patients with a maximum no of patients between 50 – 59 years with a percentage 32.1% of patients population which correlated with Milgrom et al(72) who stated that the frequency of rotator cuff tears increases with age and also correlated with Yamamoto et al (17) study.

The prevalence of rotator cuff tears was more common in males (66% of cases) involving the right shoulder (72 % of cases). The complaints given by the patient were mostly shoulder pain in 98% of cases and the history of trauma was present in only 37% of cases.

In our study the rotator cuff tear showed a significant correlation of ultrasound with MRI with a chi square value of 28.1 and p-value <0.05. The sensitivity and specificity for diagnosing rotator cuff tears were about 91.8% and specificity of 81.2% with accuracy of 88.6 %.

The most common tendon to be involved was supraspinatus muscle with prevalence of 62.6%. The supraspinatus muscle tears had a correlation between ultrasound and MRI shoulder with a chi-square value of 30.5 with p-value <0.05. The sensitivity and specificity of supraspinatus tear were 90.9 % and 85% with an accuracy of 88.6%. The supraspinatus tear was further classified into partial and full thickness tears. The partial thickness tear had sensitivity and specificity of 88.4% and specificity of 88.9% with diagnostic accuracy of 88.6%. For full thickness tears the sensitivity, specificity and accuracy were 100%. When our study was compared to a study conducted by Lisa B. McGuire et al (73) which demonstrated overall sensitivity for ultrasound was 88.3%, partial thickness tear was 83%, and total thickness tear was 95.2%. Compared to

this study, our study had better sensitivity for partial-thickness tears and full-thickness tears.

For other muscles like subscapularis, infraspinatus and teres minor, the ultrasound had a good correlation with MRI showing a score on chi square of 19.5 and p-value < 0.05. The overall sensitivity and specificity was 81.8% and 85.7% with accuracy of 84.9%.

As ultrasound is an inexpensive, non-invasive and dynamic method with high sensitivity, accuracy values and good correlation with MRI shoulder we can say that ultrasound can be used as an initial investigating and screening tool for detecting rotator cuff tears in third tier cities like Vijayapura.

LIMITATIONS

- The ultrasound probe used in our study was 9MHz linear probe for a better detection of tears and to increase the accuracy a higher resolution.
- frequency probe of 15MHz must be used.
- As ultrasound shoulder has a long learning curve in detecting tears, the sonographer should have gained more skills in detecting tears and to perform dynamic studies for impingements.
- As the prevalence of subscapularis, infraspinatus and teres minor are less, more detailed study should be done for these muscles to increase its detection rates.

CONCLUSION

Both ultrasound and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) are useful diagnostic tools for rotator cuff tears, with similar sensitivity and specificity. Ultrasound is less expensive, non-invasive, and easily accessible, making it a good screening tool for rotator cuff tears when compared to MRI but MRI is superior at defining anatomical regions where surgical correction is necessary.

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ANNEXURE - I
ETHICAL CLEARANCE

BLDE
(DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)
Declared as Deemed to be University u/s 3 of UGC Act, 1956
Accredited with 'A' Grade by NAAC (Cycle-2)

The Constituent College

SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL & RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA
BLDE (DU)/IEC/ 758/2022-23 30/8/2022

INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

The Ethical Committee of this University met on Friday, 26th August, 2022 at 3.30 p.m. in the Department of Pharmacology scrutinizes the Synopsis of Post Graduate Student of BLDE (DU)'s Shri B.M.Patil Medical College Hospital & Research Centre from ethical clearance point of view. After scrutiny, the following original/ corrected and revised version synopsis of the thesis/ research projects has been accorded ethical clearance.

TITLE: "USG VS MRI SHOULDER IN VIJAYAPURA POPULATION".

NAME OF THE STUDENT/PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR: DR JAYANTH G

**NAME OF THE GUIDE: DR SATISH PATIL & DR SANDEEP NAIK (CO-GUIDE),
Dept. of Radiology.**

Dr. Santoshkumar Jeevangi
Chairperson
IEC, BLDE (DU),
VIJAYAPURA

Institutional Ethical Committee,
BLDE (Deemed to be University)
Vijayapura

Following documents were placed before Ethical Committee for Scrutination

- Copy of Synopsis/Research Projects
- Copy of inform consent form
- Any other relevant document

Dr. Akram A. Naikwad
Member Secretary
IEC, BLDE (DU),
VIJAYAPURA

MEMBER SECRETARY
Institutional Ethics Committee
BLDE (Deemed to be University)
Vijayapura-586103, Karnataka

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ANNEXURE- II

CONSENT FORM IN ENGLISH

GUIDE : **DR. SATISH D. PATIL**

CO-GUIDE : **DR. SANDEEP NAIK**

P.G. STUDENT : **DR. JAYANTH G**

PURPOSE OF RESEARCH:

I have been informed that the purpose of this study is to correlate the findings of ultrasound shoulder with MRI in rotator cuff tears.

PROCEDURE:

I understand that I will undergo history, clinical examination, ultrasound and MRI shoulder.

RISKS AND DISCOMFORTS:

I understand that there is no risk involved in the above study.

BENEFITS:

I understand that my participation in this study will help to assess the co-rrrelation between ultrasound and MRI in rotator cuff tears for the benefit of the patient.

CONFIDENTIALITY:

I understand that the medical information produced by the study will become a part of the hospital record and will be subjected to confidentiality and privacy regulations of the hospital.

If the data is used for publications, the identity of the patient will not be revealed.

REQUEST FOR MORE INFORMATION:

I understand that I may ask for more information about the study at any time.

REFUSAL OR WITHDRAWAL OF PARTICIPATION:

I understand that my participation is voluntary and, I may refuse to participate or withdraw from the study at any time.

INJURY STATEMENT:

I understand in the unlikely event of injury to me during the study, I will get medical treatment but no further compensation. I will not hold the hospital and its staff responsible for any untoward incident during the course of the study.

Date:

DR. JAYANTH G

(Investigator)

DR. SATISH D. PATIL

(Guide)

DR. SANDEEP NAIK

(Co- Guide)

STUDY SUBJECT CONSENT STATEMENT:

I/my ward confirm that Dr. Jayanth G has explained to me the purpose of this research, the study procedure that I will undergo and the possible discomforts and benefits that I may experience in my own language.

I/my ward have been explained all the above in detail in my own language, and I understand the same. Therefore I agree to give my consent to participate as a subject in this project.

(Participant/ Guardian)

Date

(Witness to above signature)

Date

ANNEXURE- III

CONSENT FORM IN KANNADA

ಒಪ್ಪಿಗೆ ಪತ್ರ

CORRELATION OF ULTRASOUND WITH MRI SHOULDER JOINT OF ROTATOR CUFF TEAR IN POPULATION OF VIJAYAPURA

ಮಾರ್ಗದರ್ಶಿ : ಡಾ. ಸತೀಶ್ ಡಿ ಪಾಟೀಲ್

ಸಹ-ಮಾರ್ಗದರ್ಶಿ: ಡಾ. ಸಂದೀಪ್ ನಾಯಕ್

ಸ್ನಾತಕೋತ್ತರ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿ: ಡಾ. ಜಯಂತ್ ಜಿ

ಸಂಶೋಧನೆಯ ಉದ್ದೇಶ:

ಆವರ್ತಕ ಪಟ್ಟಿಯ ಮ್ಯಾಗ್ನೆಟಿಕ್ ರೆಸೋನೆನ್ಸ್ ಇಮೇಜಿಂಗ್‌ನೊಂದಿಗೆ ಅಲ್ಟ್ರಾಸೌಂಡ್ ಭುಜದ ಸಂಶೋಧನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಸ್ಪರ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸುವುದು ಈ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದ ಉದ್ದೇಶವಾಗಿದೆ ಎಂದು ನನಗೆ ತಿಳಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ.

ವಿಧಾನ:

ಈ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದ ಉದ್ದೇಶಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ವಿವರವಾದ ಇತಿಹಾಸವನ್ನು, ಕ್ಲಿನಿಕಲ್ ಪರೀಕ್ಷೆ, ಅಲ್ಟ್ರಾಸೌಂಡ್ ಮತ್ತು ಭುಜದ ಮ್ಯಾಗ್ನೆಟಿಕ್ ರೆಸೋನೆನ್ಸ್ ಇಮೇಜಿಂಗ್ಗೆ ಒಳಗಾಗುತ್ತೇನೆ ಎಂದು ನಾನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದೇನೆ.

ಅಪಾಯಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಅನಾನುಕೂಲಗಳು:

ಮೇಲಿನ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದಲ್ಲಿ ಯಾವುದೇ ಅಪಾಯವನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿಲ್ಲ ಎಂದು ನಾನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದೇನೆ.

ಪ್ರಯೋಜನಗಳು:

ಈ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದಲ್ಲಿ ನನ್ನ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯು ರೋಗಿಯ ಪ್ರಯೋಜನಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಆವರ್ತಕ ಪಟ್ಟಿಯ ಅಲ್ಟ್ರಾಸೌಂಡ್ ಮತ್ತು ಭುಜದ ಮ್ಯಾಗ್ನೆಟಿಕ್ ರೆಸೋನೆನ್ಸ್ ಇಮೇಜಿಂಗ್ಗೆ ನಡುವಿನ ಸಹ-ಸಂಬಂಧವನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಣಯಿಸಲು ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂದು ನಾನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದೇನೆ.

ಗೌಪ್ಯತೆ:

ನನ್ನ ಗುರುತನ್ನು ಯಾವುದೇ ಮೂರನೇ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿ ಅಥವಾ ಪ್ರಕಟಣೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಬಹಿರಂಗಪಡಿಸಲಾಗುವುದಿಲ್ಲ ಮತ್ತು ವೈದ್ಯಕೀಯ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯು ಆಸ್ಪತ್ರೆಯ ದಾಖಲೆಗಳ ಭಾಗವಾಗಿರುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂದು ನಾನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದೇನೆ.

ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಮಾಹಿತಿಗಾಗಿ ವಿನಂತಿ:

ನಾನು ಯಾವುದೇ ಸಮಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದ ಕುರಿತು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಕೇಳಬಹುದು ಎಂದು ನಾನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದೇನೆ.

ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಯ ನಿರಾಕರಣೆ ಅಥವಾ ಹಿಂತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವಿಕೆ:

ನಾನು ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆಗೆ ಒಪ್ಪಿಗೆಯನ್ನು ನೀಡಿದ್ದೇನೆ ಮತ್ತು ನಾನು ಯಾವುದೇ ಸಮಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಲು ನಿರಾಕರಿಸಬಹುದು ಎಂದು ನಾನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದೇನೆ

ಗಾಯದ ಹೇಳಿಕೆ:

ಅಧ್ಯಯನದ ಸಮಯದಲ್ಲಿ ನನಗೆ ಗಾಯವಾದಾಗ, ನನಗೆ ವೈದ್ಯಕೀಯ ಚಿಕಿತ್ಸೆ ನೀಡಲಾಗುತ್ತದೆ ಆದರೆ ಯಾವುದೇ ಪರಿಹಾರವನ್ನು ನೀಡಲಾಗುವುದಿಲ್ಲ ಎಂದು ನಾನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಂಡಿದ್ದೇನೆ. ಅಂತಹ ಸಂದರ್ಭಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ನಾನು ಆಸ್ಪತ್ರೆ ಮತ್ತು ಅದರ ಸಿಬ್ಬಂದಿಯನ್ನು ಹೊಣೆಗಾರರನ್ನಾಗಿ ಮಾಡುವುದಿಲ್ಲ.

ದಿನಾಂಕ:

ಡಾ. ಜಯಂತ್ ಜಿ (ತನಿಖಾಧಿಕಾರಿ).

ಡಾ. ಸತೀಶ್ ಡಿ ಪಾಟೀಲ್ (ಮಾರ್ಗದರ್ಶಿ).

ಡಾ. ಸಂದೀಪ್ ನಾಯಕ್ (ಸಹ-ಮಾರ್ಗದರ್ಶಿ).

ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ವಿಷಯದ ಒಪ್ಪಿಗೆ ಹೇಳಿಕೆ:

ಈ ಸಂಶೋಧನೆಯ ಉದ್ದೇಶ ಮತ್ತು ಕಾರ್ಯವಿಧಾನ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಭವನೀಯ ಅನಾನುಕೂಲಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಯೋಜನಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಡಾ. ಜಯಂತ್ ಜಿ ನನ್ನ ಸ್ವಂತ ಭಾಷೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ವಿವರಿಸಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಎಂದು ನಾನು ಖಚಿತಪಡಿಸುತ್ತೇನೆ.

ಆದ್ದರಿಂದ ನಾನು ಈ ಯೋಜನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ವಿಷಯವಾಗಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸಲು ಸಮ್ಮತಿಸುತ್ತೇನೆ.

(ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವವರು)

ದಿನಾಂಕ

(ಮೇಲಿನ ಸಹಿಗೆ ಸಾಕ್ಷಿ)

ದಿನಾಂಕ

ANNEXURE- IV

PROFORMA

- **Name:**

- **Age/Sex:**

- **Phone number and address:**

- **Hospital No.:**

- **Relevant complaints & history:**
 - **Time of injury:**
 - **Time of casualty consultation:**

- **Clinical findings:**
 - **Pulse Rate:** **BP:** **Spo2:**

- **USG Findings:**

- **MRI Findings:**

- **Radiological Diagnosis:**

- **Follow-up**

ANNEURE- V

MASTER CHART

AGE(Years)	SEX	Side	Shoulder Pain	Restriction of Movement	Trauma	Reactor G.I.T (month)	Suprapatellar (L&S)	Suprapatellar (M/L)	Supraspinatus Partia. (Indonesian) (L&S)	Supraspinatus Partia. (Indonesian) (M/L)	Supraspinatus Full Thickness (L&S)	Supraspinatus Full Thickness (M/L)	Other Muscles	Other Muscles
50	Male	Right	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	No
Abul Fazl Cherrand														No
57	Male	Right	YES	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	No	No	No	No
Bhomeraj Klapapa														No
58	Female	Right	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	No	No	No	Yes
Dilhad														Yes
55	Male	Left	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	No	No	No	No
Maappa														No
59	Female	Right	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	No	No	No	Yes
Morabhai														Yes
42	Female	Left	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	No	No	No	Yes
Ranabhai														Yes
52	Female	Right	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	No	No	No	Yes
Shantabai														Yes
45	Female	Right	YES	YES	YES	no	YES	YES	YES	YES	No	No	No	No
Vijaylaxmi														No
51	Female	Right	YES	NO	NO	no	YES	YES	YES	YES	No	No	No	No
Jayashree														No
50	Male	Right	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	No	No	No	No
Maappa B														No
70	Male	Right	YES	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	No	No	No	No
Malikarjun														No
46	Male	Left	YES	NO	NO	YES	NO	YES	NO	YES	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Manantaz														Yes
51	Male	Right	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	No	No	No	No
Shambu Merwade														No
62	Male	Right	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Shivappa														Yes
65	Male	Right	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Shivashankar														Yes
42	Female	Left	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	No	No	No	No
J1														No
35	Female	Right	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	No	No	No	No
Kasuri														No
54	Male	Right	YES	NO	NO	no	NO	NO	NO	NO	No	No	No	No
Nirgama														No
35	Male	Right	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	No	No	No	No
Ranangouda														No
46	Male	Left	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	No	No	No	No
Yunraj														No
29	Male	Right	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	No	No	No	No
Srihal														No
46	Male	Right	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	No	No	No	No
Ranappa														No
49	Male	Right	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Tukaram														Yes
52	Female	Left	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	No	No	No	No
Annapurna														No
30	Male	Right	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	No	No	No	No
Rakesh Sharma														No
58	Male	Right	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Gurappa														Yes
48	Male	Right	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	No	No	No	No
Shravanappa														No
33	Female	Left	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	No	No	No	Yes
Savitra														Yes
41	Male	Right	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	No	No	No	No
Mohammed Rafiq Daffadar														No
75	Male	Left	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Frappa & Baidhalil														Yes
36	Male	Left	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Maappa Shrihal Nesar														Yes
43	Female	Left	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	No	No	No	No
Kahavathi														No
55	Female	Right	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Rumaba Rathod														No
58	Male	Left	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	No	No	No	No
Dandappa														No
35	Female	Right	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	No	No	No	Yes
Kirmitika Kumar Jain														Yes
66	Female	Right	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	No	No	No	No
Kavya														No
46	Female	Right	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	No	No	No	No
Savitra														No
22	male	Right	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	No	No	No	No
Shivayagi														No
39	male	Right	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	No	No	No	No
Vinod Madar														No
45	female	Left	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	No	No	No	No
Shiba S														No
61	male	Right	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Bhramashankar Aliawani														No
40	male	Left	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	No	No	No	Yes
Saaphir Chalkhad														Yes
70	male	Right	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	No	No	No	No
Mudineab sheilin														No
48	female	Left	YES	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Suritha Bagalkot														No
60	male	Right	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	No	No	No	Yes
Harsingh Y Lamani														Yes
30	male	Right	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	No	No	No	No
Vijayakumar Basargoud														No
50	Male	Left	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	No	No	No	No
Breppa kaburji														No
50	Male	Right	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	No	No	No	No
Anu dhat														No
60	Male	Right	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	No	No	No	Yes
Yashwanth Narasappa														Yes
60	Female	Right	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Yalawa L Madar														No
62	Male	Right	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Sahasrathod														No
59	Male	Right	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	No	No	No	No
Shivanand S Hiremath														No
23	Male	Right	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	No	No	No	No
Madev Pawar														No

ANNEXURE VI
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